

WHAT IS POLITICS?		Political Science Keywords: Relations, Strategy, Regions, Partnership, Security, Peace, Negotiation, Stabilization.
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Abstract

Politics is the most important activity of organized life in society. Why and in what manner people behave in their economic and political activities should be systematically studied. Nowadays young people often declare: “I am not interested in politics”. To them politics is some disreputable art of manipulating one’s way into positions of state power for personal and party gains. In addition, they do not look forward to being called a “politician” ever in their working lives. In fact, the word has almost gradually become a term of abuse.

Different Views on Politics

As far as the concept of politics is really concerned this is a most naive and dumb notion. *Actually, we are all politicians.* Politics surrounds us everywhere, in everyday life like how much money you will need to pay your bill, how, when and how you will get the job, how much budget you will need for your family to keep them secure, where you will get educated, how you will get educated.... these are all political questions. Simply every move you make during the day, about your work, your family, your friends, behaving in traffic, community. You do not live in other planet or in a ‘no man’s land’ to avoid these everyday movement and communication, you are a part of set of laws and policies that are under the jurisdiction of a state that you live in.⁷ This mean that you play and fallow the rules that, set for everyone, and by any action you take, you are in the game. Frankly therefore whatever you do or you don’t is political one way or the other whether you like it or not. We will have to go in the past and see how mankind thought about politics from earliest time to the present day, we will try to make a difference how politics is or should be.

Politics in Greek Time

The word politics itself has its origin in the Greek word *polis*, which means the community or populace or society. Plato and Aristotle saw politics like every issue anyone would take; it will affect the whole community. In other word, politics is in community and Aristotle argued that, he who did not live in community or polis, should be either a God or a Beast. He also commented that Man is a Political Animal. At that time, Greeks were organised into small city-states or in small communities and everyone or every citizen attended in parliament meeting for deciding the affairs of the community. The Greek concept of politics included the study of man, society, state and ethics.

⁷ <https://sol.du.ac.in/mod/book/view.php?id=1599>

With the rise of large empires like Roman empire, these city-states in Greece show the necessary to add different powers to the leaders in these communities like the right of using police and military force, power and wealth and they called it government, whatever government did in the name of the state it is done by the government.

It was realised over time that politics as a study of the state and institutions of the state like the government bodies does not go deep enough into various aspects of the political life of a citizen. The ordinary citizen and his political life is an interaction between him and the society and polity of which he is a part. To understand politics therefore one has to understand the whole social process and phenomenon.⁸

After Greek period, there are different views of politics throughout history that made an impact in the world, like Liberal view, Marxist view, the Common Good view and the Power view.

The liberal view was the *individual human being* with his self-interest, enterprise, desire for richness and happiness and reason can be the foundation of a stable society. Adam Smith saw the man at that period as a selfish, egotistic being concerned only with his own self-preservation and not a social or moral being. But later on, before Marxism happened, society was not just composed of self-interested individuals but also of interest groups that can be along the lines of social, religious, cultural commercial, economic and political through which man fulfils his interests and needs.

Karl Heinrich Marx (1818-1883) was an immensely influential philosopher of German Jewish origin, a political economist, and a socialist revolutionary. While Marx addressed a wide range of issues, he is most famous for his analysis of political history in terms of class struggles, summed up in the opening line of the introduction to the Communist Manifesto: "The history of all hitherto existing society is the history of class struggles."

Marxian philosophy propounds a different view of human nature that hinges on Marx's view of human nature. According to Marxian thought "existence precedes consciousness" and who a person is, is determined by where and when he is — social context takes precedence over innate behaviour; or, in other words, one of the main features of human nature is adaptability.

Marx did not believe that all people worked the same way, or that how one works is entirely personal and individual. Instead, he argued that work is a social activity and that the conditions and forms under and through which people work are socially determined and change over time. In the Greek view of common good Plato viewed politics as a process through which men debate matters concerning the whole populace and take decisions to realize the common public good.

⁸ <https://sol.du.ac.in/mod/book/view.php?id=1599>

Aristotle saw common good as an objective thing for man for it existed in nature. He said: "The end of *polis* is not mere life, it was rather good life. *Polis* came into existence for the sake of bare means of life but it continues its existence for the sake of good life....If all communities aim at some good, the political community which is the highest of all and which embraces the rest, aims in a higher degree than any other at the highest good. The individual is for the state. The task of politics is to decide the Good'.

Even though from the earliest times it has been recognised that politics is in many ways fundamentally a study of power.

There is no single accepted definition of power. Many people have defined power differently. Sociologist Max Weber defined politics in terms of power as follows:

"Politics is the struggle to share or influence the distribution of power, whether between states or among the groups within a state. Max Weber defined power itself as 'the probability that one actor within a social relationship will be in a position to carry out his own despite resistance, regardless of the basis on which this probability rests'.⁹

Politics, Simple Explanation

Politics is the art or science of influencing other people on a civic or individual level. More narrowly, it refers to achieving and exercising positions of governance — organized control over a human community, particularly a state. A variety of methods is employed in politics, which include promoting its own political views among people, negotiation with other political subjects, making laws, and exercising force, including warfare against adversaries.

Politics is exercised on a wide range of social levels, from clans and tribes of traditional societies, through modern local governments, companies and institutions up to sovereign states, to international level.

A political system is a framework which defines acceptable political methods within a given society. Modern political discourse focuses on democracy and the relationship between people and politics. It is thought of as the way we "choose government officials and make decisions about public policy".

Politics is exciting because people disagree. They disagree about how they should live. Who should get what? How should power and other resources be distributed? Should society be based on cooperation or conflict? And so on. They also disagree about how such matters should be resolved. How should collective decisions be made? Who should have a say? How much influence should each person have? And so forth.

⁹ <https://sol.du.ac.in/mod/book/view.php?id=1599>

For Aristotle, this made politics the ‘master science’: that is, nothing less than the activity through which human beings attempt to improve their lives and create the Good Society. Politics is, above all, a social activity.

It is always a dialogue, and never a monologue. Solitary individuals such as Robinson Crusoe may be able to develop a simple economy, produce art, and so on, but they cannot engage in politics. Politics emerges only with the arrival of a Man (or Woman) Friday.

Nevertheless, the disagreement that lies at the heart of politics also extends to the nature of the subject and how it should be studied.

People disagree about what it is that makes social interaction ‘political’, whether it is where it takes place (within government, the state or the public sphere generally), or the kind of activity it involves (peacefully resolving conflict or exercising control over less powerful groups).

Disagreement about the nature of politics as an academic discipline means that it embraces a range of theoretical approaches and a variety of schools of analysis. Finally, globalizing tendencies have encouraged some to speculate that the disciplinary divide between politics and international relations has now become redundant.¹⁰

‘Politics is not a science ... but an art’, Chancellor Bismarck is reputed to have told the German Reichstag. The art Bismarck had in mind was the art of government, the exercise of control within society through the making and enforcement of collective decisions. This is perhaps the classical definition of politics, developed from the original meaning of the term in Ancient Greece.

As Adrian Leftwich proclaimed: politics is at the heart of all collective social activity, formal and informal, public and private, in all human groups, institutions and societies’.

In this sense, politics takes place at every level of social interaction; it can be found within families and amongst small groups of friends just as much as amongst nations and on the global stage. However, what is it that is distinctive about political activity? What marks off politics from any other form of social behaviour?¹¹

How you define politics

It is said that “*Politics is War without bloodshed, and War is Politics with bloodshed*” — Mao Zedong. Politics is the very system with which people rule over entire societies. Fights often

¹⁰ https://www.macmillanihe.com/resources/sample-chapters/9780230363373_sample.pdf

¹¹ What is Politics? The Activity and Its Study (2004).

break out in a society, but somehow, the nation-state prevails above all else. This is because of how a society and nation are structured. And how is it decided about the rules of these?

Politics is the tool people use that allows them to put aside their petty differences and agree on something. People are nearly impossible to corral, so when they stop fighting and agree on something, it's a miracle.

A true miracle. Politics is the miraculous tool that makes people listen, as opposed to non-stop fighting.

You know how I said that Politics is War without bloodshed? It's true, but we need to remember something.

"We don't promote war, we prepare for Peace. Peace is our profession" — Ronald Reagan.

Politics today includes the following:

The actions of the government as law making and law executing body. Policy formulation and policy implementation. The actions of the political parties and leaders aimed at achieving or retaining power. Both ethical and unethical means are in use in today's politics to achieve political goals. Mahatma Gandhi is often quoted to have said *"Politics without ethics is a sin"*. Politicians need to have some basic ethical and moral values like, honesty, service to the public etc. Our present day politicians do not have these values and thus result in huge corruption and lack of governance. David Easton called Politics as *"Authoritative allocation of values"*. Here values mean democracy, equality, liberty, justice and such other cherished goals of humanity. As long as these values are provided to the citizens by its government through politicians, there will be peace and prosperity.

Conclusion

Among all these theories and political era in the past, today we have completely different situation in politics. Nowadays those definition about politics in the past, seems to be not worthy in modern world. But yet we are still living in an organised world that have the rules and without these rules or without the politics, the world would have not existed as we know today. Politic makes the community, the states, the world more organised, more economically progressed and more secure. Nowadays politics have changed as during the history. I would quote Armando Iannucci, the Guardian journalist: *Politics was once about beliefs and society. Now it's a worship of money.*